

Education for All: Role of Universities and Higher Educational Institutions (U& HEIs)

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ABSTRACT: The role of Universities and Higher Educational Institutions in *Education for All* movement was highlighted by conferences organized by the UNESCO. Furtherance to the cause and notion, this paper further examined the scope of education for all in India and the manner Indian Universities and Higher Educational Institutions can contribute to them. However, it cannot be suggested to go for uniformity in norms, curriculum and global acceptance of certificates because norms and curriculum must be suited with the respective social objectives, needs, and availability of resources. Every social groups have different means, objectives, and style of education and it is required to value those variety instead of illogically press them and put them under burden in the name of modernity and development. Education for All would be meaningless without equal opportunities for learning so that every students in a class learns equally and became to perform equally. Therefore, it would be more logical for the government to unnecessary wasting resources in the name of standards and creating infrastructure they should try to support the respective family's and social group's efforts for education. The syllabus, curriculum, and certification should be society based. One of the right approach would be to integrating the various levels of education such as primary, secondary, and higher together. All such integrated educational institutions can provide education for various levels and also run various courses including teacher's education. Online education can be great tool for ensuring education for all as it would cut short the cost, education related transportation, mobility, and migration.

KEYWORDS: *Education for All; Uniform and Equal Education; Equal Learning; Roles of State, Society, Universities, and Industries.*

Introduction

The research was a humble attempt to look into the status of *Education for All* (EFA) and examine the current and the possible role of universities & other higher educational institutions (U & HEIs) in achieving EFA goals in both the Indian and global perspectives. It was a general assumption that U & HEIs in almost countries where there was crisis in education could contribute a lot, whereas it found that they not contributing to the extent and potential they could (UC, 2005). Therefore, to identify those areas under the purview of EFA in which Universities & HEIs could get involved or made to involve in both the global and national perspective was one of the main fundamental questions behind this research. We all knew that universities being autonomous entities in India could not expect to function as an implementing agency despite their role in some areas could extremely significant (Soilemetzidis, 2009).

There were several studies in many countries related to the manner universities were contributing to the *education for all* programs. The possible roles of universities and higher educational institutions in India in enabling *Education for All* or the "*Sarva Shiksha Abhiyan*" was also needed to be expedited in the Indian contexts. It was suggested that universities and higher education institutions could contribute greatly due to their vast resources in terms of workforce and capacity to promote education as a whole. The particular role of universities and other higher educational institutions could be in conducting research, development of curriculum, and training and orientation programs for school teachers, monitoring of programs and schools, evaluation of schemes. Further, they could develop other tools and techniques appropriately in terms of specific requirements. They could help education for all through online education, distance learning systems, and ICT and self-study promotion. In addition, students and staff unions of those institutions in cooperation of retired teachers could also do a lot to promote education for all global movements.

There were numerous demands from different quarters mostly emotional voices were heard that if a sizeable part of the

population was suffering from crisis of education then how universities and higher educational institutions would remain aloof and part without contributing. Many scholars have identified a role for the universities especially in areas such as teachers training, research, community visits and using students and staff unions in the endeavors of educating all. Even it has been suggested that by doing so universities can promote their financial status by as they generate some amount from the the budgetary allocation for education for all programs.

The global and national effort to bring the various segments of the society into the EFA (*Education for All*) process, taken together, was a recognition of the need for a broad partnership to achieve *Education for All* goals (Tang, 2010). However, the specific role of Universities in EFA was not evident in the global equation, although universities are among the most important structures for research and training of educational personnel (CICE, 2005).

Objective:

The research was having two main objectives the research objectives and the capacity building objectives. The research objectives included integration of knowledge, people, institutions, and literature around the topic. The capacity building objective included training, interactions, and field visits by the research scholar and other project staff.

Methodology:

The research was conducted mainly through mix methods using qualitative and quantitative methods both. Literature review, field visits, interviews, and case studies were performed in different parts of the country. Data analysis was done by corroborating the primary data with various secondary data using empirical. This study was mainly based upon the secondary data sources and corroborating those with empiricism and examples. Several case studies of the education institutions were conducted in different parts of the country. The data was retrieved from various government and non-governmental sources including Ministries of education at the central and state levels. Several

interviews were conducted with various stake holders in identifying their respective problems. Interviews were organized with primary teachers, secondary teachers, college teachers and professors and government administrators including district education officers, regional deputy directors, and directors as well as government secretaries and political leaders.

Review of Literature

A conference was organized by UNESCO to focus the possibility of the university's role in EFA agenda (UNESCO, 2004). How some programs under the cover of UNITWIN were organized in several countries, including India in cooperation of UNESCO and International University Cooperation (IUC) and such literatures were available in terms of proceedings, annual reports, and studies (UNITWIN, 1992).

The *Global Monitoring Report* (GMR), on EFA published by UNESCO every year also suggested that one of the problems in achieving EFA has been the lack of trained teachers and quality of curriculum (UNESCO- GMR, 2005). Both often resulted in a decrease in the *net enrollment ratio* (NER) and increase in dropouts. The role of universities and higher educational institutions considered particularly important in providing teachers education and curriculum development.

So far, ensuring higher education and technical education never put on the agenda of EFA in global terms. However, it required integrating the efforts in EFA with definite livelihood. If livelihood is not certain then we might suffer the crisis in education repeatedly even after achieving some success. There would be slipping down and examples of several African countries were highlighted in this regard (Gunga, 2009).

Some universities were offering postgraduate and undergraduate degrees in Early Childhood, Primary, Literacy and Adult Education. They were also involved in short-term training for educational professionals. This was particularly true for developed countries. Nonetheless, developing countries were also making an effort to involve universities in EFA. Some countries had taken the policy decision requiring all lecturers in primary teacher training institutions to have at least a first degree. Universities and other institutions of higher learning called upon to use their comparative advantage to be more visible with the EFA agenda (S. M. Sungoh, 2009).

To be effective, universities must take into consideration that achievement of EFA goals is the hub for social transformation and sustainable development. It is not surprising that country advocate for education both as a right and as a need. The challenge of the country is not only to make the changes for improvements demanded by EFA movement, but also to maintain such changes in the education system.

Problem

There are tremendous data gap especially related to the manner universities and higher educational institutions can be contributing to the education for all in India. It was also needed to classify the overall objectives of education for all and how it is important to achieve those goals. It was also not certain that does education for all a government business or every sections of the society would be involved in it. The international educational index is how relevance to the India contexts was also not very clear. So much so that what is the benefits of ensuring net enrollment, pass outs, and dropouts was not made clear. Some students learns quickly and in this case is it proper to keep students engaged for such a long period because education period

has been unnecessarily enhanced. After all it was also not clear that what a student will contribute to the society and respective families and what would be their role in the society. If there would be unequal compensation by the government, industries, and market students would tend to opt for such professions and roles that would ensure higher income or returns and in this manner they may compromise with the core social objectives and support individual objectives.

Government through National Council of Teachers Education has been engaged in regulating teacher's education in the country. Teacher's training has been made compulsory for teachers and large numbers of teachers training institutions have come up in the country. Why it was not considered to allow already existed colleges and universities to engage them in teacher's education. If existing institutions would have been given scope then there would not be extra burden to create infrastructure and arrange resources. Moreover, it has not been established that a trained teacher would be better educating their students.

Most of learning in India in traditional manner used to be done by private teachers and tutors either in home based manner either at the student's or teacher's home. Such system is deep rooted in most of Indian societies and have acquired reputation and trust for ease in accessibility and cost effectiveness. There are numerous society based teachers and tutors who are engaged in teaching students at various levels of primary, secondary, higher and even technical.

Government faces tremendous difficulties in preparing curriculum, syllabus and text books. Sometimes all these jobs become so controversial. Instead of going for a unified approach, a diversified approach would have been more effective and useful also. A government institutions mostly remained problematic and they cannot be expected to solve people's problems. Most of universities and schools suffered from a crisis of teachers due to adopting contradictory approaches. On one hand teachers were provided sixth and seventh pay scale and on the others hand most of education was done by guest faculties and contractual teachers. It has created tensions in the education system. Universities are not able to standardize the various subjects and setting and Indian models and standards in different subjects. Even they are mostly found following the American or European models without considering their utility and futility. Largely publications are being done in English ignoring our own Indian languages. Even English used as language in many such literatures mostly remained substandard. Even India failed to develop its own language based computer systems and tools.

Most of educational institutions in India have turned into a degree providing institutions. Students get enrolled at any recognized institutions just for degree however, they used to learn through private coaching and tuition. Even many government teachers run their own coaching centres in many parts of India. Due to contradictory regulating approached most of government institutions have become also most redundant as they failed to produce their own knowledge. People have lost their trust in those institutions. For the vote politics government remained engaged in populist measures that has adversely affected the performance of many educational institutions. There are lack of honesty, impartiality, and fairness in education. This can be also true in case of recruitments. Private institutions and universities are coming up in numbers and they would realize handsome amount as fees. Many students would not be able to pay such handsome fees. Sighting thus opportunity government

has come up with schemes of student's credit card. Even financial institutions were providing study loans. Many scholars have taken such instances as burdening the childhood with loans. Even there is no guarantee of employment or self-employment after education. Startups, skill development, and vocational courses have become more popular than regular courses.

The case of governments worldwide, including some developed country day by day became troublesome. With massive privatization of capital formation, there was less and less creation of real wealth for the funding of social welfare measures. However, in India it could see that traditional family, societies ensured education, health, livelihood, agriculture and horticulture through a sizeable part of the course of history. However, it could find increasingly that how democratic governments failed due to the stakes. Now government also doing everything that they could not do. The basic functions suggested for the governments could be maintaining law and order, maintaining courts, judiciary, security of citizens and promoting social security. There could never be the only method of ensuring social security that the government implemented every program on its own, whereas it could directly provide funds to individuals, families in crisis to overcome. However, that could see that government indulging in every sector without performing and making a mess. Governments were engaged in borrowing huge amounts from international agencies in terms of logistics and development and adding unwanted pressure on the government exchequer and people at large. Government must clear cut draw its line of action and not involve in sectors where it had long history of failures and instead of learning lessons from repeated failures it stop trying to graduate over past failures that landed them in more trouble all most all the time. Government must leave certain things to the individuals, family and societies however, must provide social security arrangements including protection of livelihood. It could direct finance to individuals and families instead of starting programs on its own that bound to suffer from deficiencies due to stakes most of the time.

The country was facing tremendous problems in the field of education that made government to ensure several developmental initiatives launched in the country. On one side, we could see the launch of "Sarva Shiksha Abhiya" Mid-Day Meal Schemes, Free Books, Dresses and Bicycles in some states and scholarships to meritorious and girl child. All those efforts resulted in an increase in the net enrollment ration (NER) however the quality of education, teachers, infrastructure, dropouts and suspension of programs emerged as a major hurdle. We could not assume successful only on the basis of increase in Net Enrollment Ration because we must look to ensure quality of education across the country at par with international standards, enabling higher and technical education to meritorious and deserving students all required working out which would emerge as a great problem in coming years.

There were several components of the EFA programs being implemented under the aegis of EFA definitely had qualitative and a logical role for Universities & HEIs. After all it may be a question of morality too, because when a sizeable part of the population was suffering from crisis of education, then how universities could live aloof and apart without contributing to the global efforts aimed at providing *Education for All*. Probably the critical question was not what universities can contribute to EFA but rather why the work of universities was not integrated in the EFA.

The role of universities further acquired weight because education has been always an integrated subject, hence it would not be wise to see and deal education separately in primary, secondary, higher & professional education. If we would continue to do as this then we would bound to deviate from our mission.

It was not easy to identify areas and manner of involvement of U & HEIs because both have an extremely different mandate of their origin and it was also never easy to match mandates of the university and EFA community to draw some commonality and agreeable points. It was needed to establish that if EFA was achievable then universities & higher educational institutions must have to play a role.

Findings

It is needed to associate the education system, curriculum, and certification with the respective social problems and objectives. The involvement of Universities & HEIs with EFA programs would be beneficial if decisions are taken with great application of mind. Teachers training can be started in all those colleges and universities and it would cut short the requirement of resources and infrastructure that would be needed in setting up new teachers training institutes. University can take up research project that would be beneficial in measuring the outcome and monitoring. In addition, universities and higher educational institutions can make an outreach to educationally deficient areas through its students, teachers, and staff associations. It would help in sustaining the education process at the micro levels. Universities and higher educational institutions can work as resource centres for primary and secondary educational institutions in their respective areas.

The education for all is an educational arrangement program as it makes a government to allocate and regulate properly the education sector especially at the primary levels. So far education for all is not so focused the secondary and higher education. Certainly it has supported a great role of the government and functioning of the governments in India has not been so far satisfactory in many parts of the country. Considering various failures it was not considered proper to support a wider role by the government in the education sector. There can be alternate arrangements through which such efforts would have been better focused. Even the government can develop alternatives to support education after merging its efforts with the social efforts.

Education for all just focused hard targets to be achieved and never applied mind in a manner those hard targets would be realized. Everything cannot be achieved with mere allocation of resources by the government and funding unproductive institutions and schemes. Midday meal, free books, dresses, and bicycles would increase enrollment however, it would not guarantee quality and equal learning. Even it never bothered about the transportation of students as numerous lives lost in transporting students between schools and home. The quality of teachers and irregularity in admissions and evaluations makes news most often. Though there could definitely some valid instances that universities and higher educational institutions were playing role in achieving EFA goals, but their role was not comprehensive whereas urgent need felt to further integrate universities and higher educational institutions with EFA. It could be said that most of those international educational indicators on which the educational index of the respective countries has been based could not be termed realistic and

relevant to India. All those indicators would not ensure value social produce and behavior. The GDP of the country would not necessarily improve if everyone would achieve a PhD. Therefore, a utility and futility of a particular education was not evaluated properly. The course was made lengthy, confusing and illogical.

During the research, it could find that the education system in India suffers from crisis due to poor socio - economic status. The high population growth, mixed with lack of resources resulted in inability of parents and societies to contribute to education. The problem of child labor and dropouts could directly relate to population growth and lack of sustainable livelihood. Several reports highlighted the quality of education not satisfactory due to a faulty selection process of teachers and nominal amount paid as salary. In fact, the schemes like *Sarva Shiksha Abhiyan* and *Mid-Day Meal* formulated during the control of inflation, however, massive increase of inflation very excessively out budgeting the entire process.

Universities could play more significant role in producing more women teachers because some experience had shown that women teachers were better for girl students. Therefore, by promoting women teachers, we can achieve "gender parity and equality" (OXFAM, 2009).

India like some other countries was lacking on the front of online and open school/ university system. India so far was not having any online schooling or university system. In addition, some open universities were not at par with the requirement and as a result open universities were crowded and found to be compromising on quality most often.

It could establish that courses of study or syllabus related to various segments of education and training programs were country or region specific. It was required that courses, curriculum and certificates would have across the border acceptance for the sake of quality.

Universities in India had the advantage of having various disciplines. They offered fields of study that must converge for the effective implementation of EFA. Such fields included health, public health, science and technology, engineering, social sciences and research. They could contribute to reaching EFA goals from various angles, such as improving the quality of education through personnel training and research that could help to foster the right to education and inform national and international policies.

U & HEIs in both the global and national perspectives, it could further identify that U & HEIs had a specific role in achieving gender parity- equality, providing teacher's training, curriculum development, global accreditation of courses and certificates across the border, research and evaluation of different programs, IEC and community service through students and teachers' associations.

Conclusion:

The role of Universities and Higher Education Institutions may be in enabling quality teachers, conducting research, and working as resource centres for preparation of educational

materials, and other tools. However, it would be more beneficial to recognized and include the respective efforts of numerous individual and social groups. The traditional systems of education such as *Gurukul*, *Madrasa*, and *Montessori* are still prevalent in India. They have commanded respect and reputation for many reasons. It needed to support those society based efforts. And it never required to suppress those efforts in the name of standards, modernity, development, and globalization. Such society based institutions can easily ensure education for all.

Acknowledgement

Author acknowledges its gratitude for the University Grants Commission for sanctioning the project. In addition, author also acknowledges gratitude towards all individuals and institutions that supported in the study

Declaration:

There is no any declared conflict of interests by the author.

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